

TYPHLOPEDAGOGIC METHODS OF EDUCATION OF VISUALLY DISABLED CHILDREN

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Abstract. *Forming the young generation into a well-rounded person is a very responsible task. Our humanitarian country cares about the growth and education of every child and takes children with disabilities under social protection. They help them find their place in life. It creates the necessary conditions for the education of children with special educational needs. In particular, the attention and opportunities given to visually impaired children are commendable.*

This article describes the need for pedagogues involved in the education of blind and visually impaired children to have information about their vision levels and diseases, and to use pedagogical tools in the classroom.

Keywords: *pedagogy, blind, visually impaired, education, rehabilitation.*

Introduction

The eye is one of the important analyzer organs in human life. A child can see, hear, smell and taste from the day he is born.

Gradually, he tries to know, sense and perceive the existence around him. A child's imagination develops a lot in the first years of his life. When he reaches the age of two, he begins to distinguish objects from each other according to their color, shape, and size. Various sensory abilities develop in him: seeing and examining, listening and hearing, external signs of things such as distinguishing by looking, imitating what the eye sees and the ear hears. This is of great importance for the child's mental development.

Visually impaired children begin to understand all the information they receive through their eyes by relying on their auditory and sensory abilities. They learn to have an idea about the color, shape, movement, distance and proximity of objects and their place in space and learn to use them by touching them with their hands. This category includes parents in families with children. It is very important for educators and teachers to be aware of pedagogical knowledge and skills when working in preschool and general secondary education institutions.

Research materials and methodology

On the basis of the relevant articles of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. LRU- No 641 dated 15.10.2020 "On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities" [1.], our state pays great attention to the comprehensive support of children with disabilities being directed.

Article 8 of this law: Based on the principle of respecting the developing abilities of children with disabilities and the right to preserve their individuality,

Children with disabilities should fully enjoy all human rights and freedoms on a par with other children, develop harmoniously in all aspects, have support in their social activity and interest in work, education, science, technology. In order to attract them to art and sports, it is stated that the priority of the interests of children with disabilities is considered a priority in all actions performed in relation to them. Also, the education of visually impaired children depends on the development of the field of Typhlopedagogy and its wide application in practice.

“Typhlopedagogy (derived from the Greek word tyflos - blind) - science of education of blind children” [5. 6.] It is important that this subject is related to Ophthalmology, Pediatrics, and Psychology.

There are two types of visual impairment: Congenital and Acquired. Congenital visual impairment is caused by genetic or developmental damage to the embryo. Acquired visual impairment occurs as a result of an accident or a complication of another disease.

“Children with vision problems are divided into 2 types according to visual acuity:

1. Totally blind - children with 0 percent visual acuity read and write based on Braille.
2. Partially blind children with visual acuity up to 0.05 can read and write in simple script using preserved vision.

Visually impaired people are divided into the following types according to their visual acuity:

1. Visual acuity from 0.05 to 0.1;
2. Visual acuity from 0.1 to 0.2;
3. Visual acuity is from 0.2 to 0.4.

Blind children learn educational material in class mainly based on tactile perception and auditory perception. It is necessary to create appropriate sanitary and hygienic conditions for children who have to wear glasses. The child's workplace should be properly and adequately lit. Attention is paid to how clearly the child sees the blackboard, table, pictures drawn on cards and other educational materials. Taking into account that the eyes of children with refraction in need of special help get tired quickly, it is required to change the types of work for them as much as possible during the lesson, to strictly control the volume of work and tasks related to eye gaze” [3. 5.].

The textbook “Special pedagogy” recommended by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan [6. 295.] provides information on eye diseases and the level of vision. According to him, even visually impaired children have different levels of vision. People who can't see long distances or can't see near, but can't see far, can't distinguish colors (colorblind). It is necessary to use adapted methods for visually impaired children.

Children with refraction are in need of special help. In near vision, distant objects are seen vaguely, when explained more clearly, there are difficulties in observing a distant object, reading, writing, and drawing pictures while walking. Children with this type of disease should not bend their head for a long time, bend down quickly, lift heavy objects, shake their body, or work with small objects for a long time. Dim lighting is prohibited.

Farsightedness - in this case, objects are seen far away. It is difficult to understand objects close to the eyes. Children with this disease have a hard time seeing small objects and have trouble reading, writing, and mastering handouts. They are not prohibited from performing physical tasks, but they are prohibited from working with close objects for a long time.

Amblyopia is observed in some children. This disease is caused by poor eyesight. In this case, a two-sided problem is formed. In this disease, it is very difficult to read and write, draw, study maps and tables.

Nystagmus is an involuntary rhythmic repetitive eye movement. In this case, the images in the viewing environment appear to spread. In this case, the child cannot concentrate. It is especially difficult to perceive objects in motion.

Astigmatism is a combination of far and near vision. Rays are refracted incorrectly as a result of corneal deformity. As a result of skewed perception in vertical, horizontal and other directions on the retina of children with this disease, an incorrect image of the shape of the body appears in their imagination.

Such diseases include cataracts, optic nerve atrophy, albinism, microphthalmia and others.

Cataract is clouding of the eyeball. This disease is treated by surgically removing the gem and replacing it with a new one.

Aphasia is the absence of a gem.

The function of the cornea is to refract light. Physical tasks are limited in children with aphasia and ataxia.

Visual atrophy can also be observed as a result of brain injuries, retinal diseases, brain tumors, optic nephritis. In this case, the eye is disconnected from the center. This disease cannot be cured. However, it is necessary to prevent secondary defects arising from it. It should not take more than 5-10 minutes to teach children with this disease by eye.

Pigment retinent is a disorder of the activity of rods in the retina. In this case, there is a narrowing of the field of vision or its complete loss. There is no cure for the disease.

Albinism is a lack of pigment in the retina. In this case, the child's eyes will be red, hair and body will be white. It is recommended to protect them from sunlight.

The outer layer of the retina leaks. Children with myopia are often prone to this condition. They can't do heavy lifting or exercise. Continuous work with them should not exceed 5 minutes.

Literature analysis

S. Dangalov, a researcher who has contributed to the development of the science of pedagogy, the author of the work "History of pedagogy and its importance" [4. 15.] where the names of the following scientists who worked in this field and left great methodical discoveries are listed in the methodical recommendation: V. Gayui, the founder of the science of pedagogy, took the first initiative to teach visually impaired children, he established special educational institutions in Russia. His self-sacrifice serves as the basis for the development of this field to this day.

1. We all know that Braille's six-dot relief writing has brought blind people from darkness to light all over the world.

Y.B. Ryabkin discovered innate and acquired forms of color discrimination.

The professor of Leningrad Pedagogical Institute named after A.I. Gersem, B.I. Kovalenko made a great contribution to the development of this science and to the development of methods of teaching general education subjects to the blind.

M.I. Zemsova, A.I. Litvak, V. Fromm, Y. Yasensky - studied the specific features of the development of thinking according to the degree of visual impairment.

Among the Uzbek scientists, in 2005, Sh.Khalilova conducted research on the topic "Characteristics of thinking of visually impaired children" and O. Rustamov on the topic "Formation of mathematical concepts in visually impaired children".

Among the young scientists: D. Sulonova, N. Obidova, Z. Djalolova conducted research on the study and improvement of the specific aspects of pedagogical and correctional work with children with visual impairments, published textbooks, training manuals, programs and articles.

Discussion and results

Visual acuity levels are more likely to decline with age in adults, and may improve in children with good rehabilitation.

Dealing with the education of visually impaired children is twice as responsible and difficult as that of healthy children. Because visual defects affect the child's mental and physical development, and if the child's education is not properly formed, it can acquire another secondary defect.

It is necessary to create the necessary conditions to arouse the interest of visually impaired students in education, to satisfy their needs for independent learning, and to take into account their opportunities in developing their attitude to social life. Also, it is necessary to systematically implement issues such as formation of knowledge and skills in creative activity, career guidance. It is necessary to carry out educational activities such as comprehensive development and support of the blind child's personality, formation of confidence in self-expression, appropriate assessment of aspirations, and the manifestation of individual abilities. In addition, it is appropriate to strengthen efforts to prepare them for independent life by helping them not only mentally, but also physically, enriching their knowledge of personal hygiene, teaching them a healthy lifestyle and hard work. The solution and essence of these urgent issues can be revealed only and only in the field of child education.

“Teachers and educators dealing with children with visual impairments should demonstrate the priority of the pedagogic and psychological approach to them in all forms of education. To do this, first of all, determining the level of vision of children is the first step in this regard. That is, they will have to find out at what age blind children lost their sight, how far the vision of a visually impaired child is, and the type of disease according to the doctor's opinion about his health” [2. 153.].

In teaching children with visual impairments, it is important to determine their vision levels and use teaching methods accordingly. Including:

In the implementation of education for blind children with 0% vision, methods aimed at strengthening their perceptual abilities are used. It should also be noted that children of this type have lost their ability to see due to eye diseases, which are congenital and acquired (depending on how old they were acquired). It is very important to have relevant information. Otherwise, it will be possible to harm his health. The later the child's blindness begins, the richer his vision of existence will be and the easier it will be to improve it.

Visually impaired children can study in boarding schools “Nurli Maskan” and general education schools according to the wishes of their parents or equivalent persons. However, before sending the child to an educational institution, it is advisable to have him examined by an Ophthalmologist and choose a place of study based on the recommendation of a specialist.

Education of visually impaired children in special kindergartens and schools consists of such factors as preserving their visual abilities, making corrections and preventing secondary mental complications in the future.

Conclusion

It can be concluded that if sufficient conditions are created for blind children to receive education in a suitable place for them, if the necessary typhlopedagogic methods and correction work are properly organized, if they are supported in every way, there is no doubt that such children will grow up to contribute to the society, have their own profession, and have high morale.

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